

Advanced Multifield Models for Wave Propagation Analysis in Smart Composite Panels

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Introduction

Commercial plate models tend to underestimate the stresses to-the-thickness directions. Taking the Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) as an example:

CLT

$$\begin{aligned} u_x &= u_{x0} + \varphi_x z \\ v_y &= v_{y0} + \varphi_y z \\ w_z &= w_{z0} \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{zz} &= \frac{\partial w_z}{\partial z} = 0 \\ \varepsilon_{xz} &= \frac{\partial u_x}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w_z}{\partial x} = \varphi_x \end{aligned}$$

- zero to-the-thickness strain
 - constant shear strain

➔ Higher order plate models are required to predict the non-negligible to-the-thickness behaviour in laminated structures.

Numerical Model

FE Model based on the Carrera Unified Formulation (CUF), developed by the MUL2 Group

$$U(u, v, w, \phi) = N_i(x, y) \cdot F_\tau(z)$$

$N_i(x, y)$

$F_\tau(z)$

- 2D element mesh
- FE model kinematics
- Can be refined in the commercial FEM tools by either refining the mesh or increasing the order of the used shape function
- Can be refined to a high order with:
 - **Equivalent Single Layer (ESL) expansion**
 - Taylor Expansion Polynomials

Linear element

quadratic element

cubic element

➤ Taylor Expansion Polynomials

• Layer-Wise expansion

➤ Lagrange Polynomials

Objectives

Modelling Lamb wave propagation in smart composite panels

- ❖ Orthotropic material $[0,90,90,0]_s$ with surface mounted piezoelectric transducers
- ❖ Coupled electro-mechanical finite element two-dimensional (2D) plate models
- ❖ Study the effect of using advanced higher order kinematics on the Time-Of-Flight (TOF)
- ❖ Reduce the computational cost by the implementation of Node Dependent kinematics

Benchmark Problem

Figure 1: Actuation signal at 600 kHz

Figure 2: Benchmark problem with the actuators and sensors positioned, in mm

Results

Figure 3: Antisymmetric wave propagation under refined elements and model kinematics

Figure 4: Symmetric wave propagation showing the number of timestep and model kinematics effect on the obtained error

Figure 5: Wave propagation and TOF between points A and B

Figure 6: NDK results for a propagating A_0 Lamb wave

Conclusions

- Higher order model kinematics give satisfactory results
- It is essential to perform time step refinement
- Low order model kinematics produce positive error resulting in a stiffer structure

- Less timestep refinement produces a negative error
- The above errors may cancel out, but the problem is case dependent
- Using NDK for A_0 reduces the computational cost by 60% with an error less than 0.15% compared to a fully refined model

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